

Status Quo, Issues and Measures related to
the Protection of Industrial Heritage in Japan

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1. Introduction

With the inscription of the Tomioka Silk Mill and Related Sites on the World Heritage List in 2014 and that of the Sites of Japan's Meiji Industrial Revolution in July 2015, the number of industrial heritage of Japan inscribed on the World Heritage List totals three – the two just mentioned and Iwami Ginzan Silver Mine and Its Cultural Landscape. However, this is not something to be simply rejoiced with. In recent years, it seems that the true meaning of world heritage is becoming lost. One cannot help but think that in reality the wish to conserve nature and culture for mankind is being replaced by the desire to increase places for tourism. One cannot help but wonder what value there may be in conserving a tourist spot that has simply acquired greater value by becoming a “world heritage” when many people do not understand the true value of that place. This having been said, some may then wonder what little value a “world heritage” has, especially in Japan.

Of course, that is not the case. Conventionally, in order to be inscribed as a world heritage, the government must first acknowledge the cultural value of the industrial heritage and guarantee to protect it as a cultural property. In the present case, the government of Japan has also promised to protect the various sites inscribed in the Sites of Japan's Meiji Industrial Revolution as cultural heritage. Nevertheless, its composite elements include properties still in regular use, and the fact is that they are the assets of private enterprises. In this regard, the Agency for Cultural Affairs, which is conventionally in charge of the protection of cultural properties, does not have a system with which to protect them. Instead, the measure provided by the government is to have a separate national institution organize a temporary committee to take on the task of protecting such properties. If UNESCO has recognized such a system, then who is to question it? However, a great anxiety remains as to whether this system is effective in protecting cultural

properties satisfactorily.

Because of such a concern and also because the protection of industrial heritage in Japan is a subject of much discussion recently, this matter will be examined and some of the issues involved will be pointed out.

2. Status quo of the protection of cultural properties in Japan

First, the status quo concerning the protection of cultural properties in Japan will be introduced.

Today, the administration of the protection of cultural properties in Japan is, from the point of view of organization, undertaken by three divisions in the Agency for Cultural Affairs – Monuments and Sites, Architecture, and Fine Arts – with each division being in charge of different types of cultural properties.

- Monuments and Sites Division is in charge of the protection of shell mounds, ancient tombs, palace sites and other sites which are of high historic or scientific value; gardens, seashores, mountains and places of scenic beauty which are of high artistic or aesthetic value; and animals, plants, and minerals and geological features which are of high scientific value.
- The Architecture Division is in charge of the protection of buildings and other structures including civil engineering structures that possess high historic, artistic or scientific value that are designated either as important cultural properties or national treasures.
- With regard to works of fine and applied arts, the Fine Arts Division is in charge of tangible objects that possess high historic, artistic or scientific value, such as paintings, sculptures, applied art works, books and documents. These are designated as important cultural properties or national treasures and protected.

(cf. “An Overview of Japan’s Policies on the Protection of Cultural Properties, Agency for Cultural Affairs, FY2001)

Under this system, these cultural properties are investigated by the Agency and designated accordingly. Once designated, the responsibility of maintaining their present condition lies with the owners or groups in charge of their management, but the government will provide a certain amount of subsidy for their restoration. This is the way in which nationally designated cultural properties are protected in Japan.

However, an examination of the present system of administration concerning the protection of cultural properties reveals well how it is not appropriate for the protection of industrial heritage. A mismatch occurs because, in the current administrative system for the protection of cultural properties, designation is based on the value of an individual property, but for the protection of industrial heritage the entire system surrounding it needs to be protected.

3. What is industrial heritage ?

According to the Charter of the International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage*²:

Industrial heritage consists of the remains of industrial culture which are of historical, technological, social, architectural or scientific value. These remains consist of buildings and machinery, workshops, mills and factories, mines and sites for processing and refining, warehouses and stores, places where energy is generated, transmitted and used, transport and all its infrastructure, as well as places used for social activities related to industry such as housing, religious worship or education.

The Charter continues with the following comments on the values of industrial heritage:

- I. The industrial heritage is the evidence of activities that have had and continue to have profound historical consequences. The motives for protecting the industrial heritage are based on the universal value of this evidence, rather than on the singularity of unique sites.
- II. The industrial heritage is of social value as part of the record of the lives of ordinary men and women, and as such it provides an important sense of identity. It is of technological and scientific value in the history of manufacturing, engineering, construction, and it may have considerable aesthetic value for the quality of its architecture, design or planning.
- III. These values are intrinsic to the site itself, its fabric, components, machinery and setting, in the industrial landscape, in written documentation, and also in the intangible records of industry contained in human memories and customs.

- IV. Rarity, in terms of the survival of particular processes, site typologies or landscapes, adds particular value and should be carefully assessed. Early or pioneering examples are of especial value.

As is evident, industrial heritage does not refer to an individual building or machine; rather, its value is to be recognized only if the entire system surrounding the industry or the site is preserved in its entirety.

4. Preservation of industrial heritage in Japan and issues

Recently in Japan, the value of industrial heritage is beginning to be better understood. For instance, heritage like the Sado Complex of Heritage Mines, Primarily Gold Mines (hereafter, the Sado Mines) consists of facilities related to the entire process of gold manufacturing, from the mining of gold ore to its pulverization, selection, refinement and manufacture of oval gold coins (*koban*) on the Island of Sado, as well as to the coins themselves. Furthermore, the fact that the port from which the coins were loaded on boats to be shipped to Honshu, the main island of Japan, still remains also contributes to its high evaluation. In addition, gold mines have been found and documents that describe the history of mining from the start until the closing of the mines remain. In this sense, too, this heritage is highly evaluated. Currently, it is also on the tentative list for inscription on the World Heritage List and steps are being taken for deliberation.

The following section will focus on the issues related to the preservation of industrial heritage in Japan as represented by the Sado Mines.

The Sado Complex of Heritage Mines, Primarily Gold Mines is the site of gold and silver mines located in Sado City, Niigata Prefecture (Island of Sado). Remains that reveal the process of refinement of gold and silver, from the procurement of raw materials to the manufacture of products, as has been noted earlier, can still be found on the island. Although it is protected now in accordance with the administration for the protection of cultural properties in Japan, there are two issues with regard to their protection as industrial heritage.

The first issue is that many of these places have been designated as monuments (in other words, as places of high historic or scientific value) and duly protected. In this case, as a matter of fact, buildings on the land and machinery inside these buildings are evaluated merely as things that exist on the land. In a

sense, this is an extremely unstable condition. In other words, since it is not the value of the buildings or machinery themselves that is recognized, it is possible that proper treatment may not be executed when the need for restoration of the land, buildings or machinery should arise if the person in charge at the Agency does not have much interest in the buildings or machinery. An explanation may be needed here since it may be difficult for those not familiar with the bureaucratic structure in Japan: in Japan it is not always the case that professionals in given disciplines serve as government officials.

The second issue is that recently some of the buildings on the designated complex were designated as important cultural properties (the value of the buildings themselves were recognized). This is to be welcomed from the point of view of protecting the buildings, but in reality only some of the buildings were designated and the majority of buildings and machinery were not. The reason is clear, at least from the point of view of the Agency for Cultural Affairs – the undesignated ones, as individual properties, are not valuable enough for designation. That in itself is not beyond understanding, but that in itself is a problem for the preservation of industrial heritage. As was mentioned earlier, industrial heritage is preserved upon the concept that the entire system with all its composite elements should be preserved. In this sense, it is highly possible that problems may arise in the future if some buildings and machinery in the same industrial heritage are not designated while others are. In other words, should there be a need for restoration in the future, if the person in charge at the Agency does not understand the situation, they may be treated as valueless. This phenomenon, too, may arise from a characteristic peculiar to Japan and may be difficult for those unfamiliar with the Japanese bureaucracy to understand, but as officials tend to change positions every three years or so, sometimes transfer of duties from an official to his successor may not be sufficient and information may not be passed on correctly.

All this may sound as though the problem in Japan lies in the government officials. However, that is not the case. The problem is in the system of the protection of cultural properties more than in the officials. The problem is in the fact that the land, buildings, and machinery that exist in the same location as the industrial heritage are not evaluated equally as industrial heritage but that they

are first evaluated individually and then designated by the government.

Another example is that of Ashio Copper Mine, which is located in the northern part of Nikko in Tochigi Prefecture. Its facilities are scattered over an area approximately 20km along the Watarase River and its surrounding valley. It, too, consists of facilities that have been designated historic sites and a steel bridge, Furukawa-bashi, that has been designated an important cultural property, like in the case of Sado.

Ashio Copper Mine was discovered in the mid-15th century and by 1610 was producing copper under the direct control of the Tokugawa shogunate (government). By the latter half of the 17th century, it produced 1/5 of the copper exported from Nagasaki. However, production suddenly declined and by the end of the shogunate the mine was all but closed. In 1877 Furukawa Ichibei, the founder of the Furukawa conglomerate, undertook its re-development and from about 1884 the amount of production increased greatly. Efforts were made to expand production by introducing state-of-art machinery from the West, but it was also around this time that cases of mineral poisoning began to occur. Although production continued even through the time of the two World Wars and the Korean War, the mine was finally closed in 1973. Ore refining using imported mineral continued but it, too, was terminated in 1989. Today facilities of those days remain partially.

What may be recognized as being important about Ashio Copper Mine is the fact that a great number of machinery that was used at the time remains. Honzan Refinery, the major refinery, has been demolished due to the aging of its facilities and safety purposes, but the buildings and machinery at the Tsudo Flotation and Dressing Plant remain. As far as the present author is aware, this is the only place in Japan where such machinery remains. Even though such important machinery must be preserved, as in the case of Sado, the value of these buildings and machinery has not been recognized and they have not been designated important cultural properties.

Another large issue at Ashio is the fact that many of the facilities are owned by Furukawa Co. Ltd. and protection by the administration is difficult. Of course, much of the Sado Mines is still owned by private enterprises, but since its management is done by the city of Sado, this problem of protection has been solved there. However, in Ashio matters have not yet proceeded to that stage. It seems that

this is greatly due to the side of the enterprise. The enterprise continues, even today, to conduct quality management of matters discharged from the mine, including water, at many of the existing facilities. For this reason, these facilities are considered to be in actual operation and cannot be opened to tourists. Thus, it is difficult for administrative bodies to execute preservation and restoration measures.

5. Plans for improvement

What then should be done? Consideration must be given as to what is necessary in order to protect industrial heritage, a new type of cultural property. To do this, it is essential to acknowledge the fact that protection of industrial heritage is difficult within the protective system of Japan wherein cultural properties are categorized into three types. It must be acknowledged that a system in which only the value of land is considered in order to protect the land, in which only the value of a building is considered in order to protect the building, in which only the value of a machine is considered in order to protect that machine cannot respond to the needs of industrial heritage. A quick way to solve this problem is to create a new category called "industrial heritage" (or modern cultural heritage). Designation under this category will be decided upon consideration of the value as industrial heritage. If it is decided to possess high value, its related area, buildings and machinery will all be included within the range of designation and become targets for protection by the nation.

Of course, in making this new category, financial considerations are indispensable. In other words, many of the cultural properties conventionally referred to as modern cultural heritage are large-scale objects such as dams, bridges and water-purification facilities. If the conventional system is to be applied in restoring such objects, the government will have to subsidize half of the expenses. If this system is to be applied for industrial heritage, it is evident that a huge amount of money will be necessary. So, some ways to reduce the burden of the government need to be devised. For instance, by expanding the range of designation as industrial heritage, in other words by establishing a new category of designation, restrictions regarding utilization might be slightly mitigated while the rate of government subsidy itself is reduced.

Another matter that must be considered is how the issue of financial support may be improved. Until now, the burden of subsidy was shared by several executive bodies such as the nation, prefectures, and cities. But in the future, such a system will become difficult. A new system by which the burden may be shared more widely by society in general needs to be considered.

A final comment to be made is that the plans for improvement which have been suggested are, at this point, still the author's/ personal thoughts. It does not necessarily mean that Japan as a nation is moving toward such a direction.

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*² The International Committee for the Conservation of the Industrial Heritage